

Table S1 Whole-rock major and trace elemental compositions of studied early Devonian A-type granites together with previously published geochemical data of coeval A-type granites in Beishan Orogenic Belt.

Lithology	K-feldspar granite	K-feldspar granite	Granite	K-feldspar granite	K-feldspar granite	K-feldspar granite	K-feldspar granite	Mylonitic granite	Mylonitic granite	Granitodiorite
Samples	Nan 16BS005	16BS006	16BS007	16BS123	16BS124	16BS125	16BS117	16BS118	16BS119	16BS120
Tectonic Unit	Huanishan unit						Mazongshan unit			
SiO ₂	76.99	76.70	77.38	74.02	76.55	74.47	75.51	73.48	74.93	68.09
TiO ₂	0.17	0.17	0.14	0.28	0.15	0.25	0.26	0.03	0.05	0.62
Al ₂ O ₃	11.98	12.12	11.85	13.19	12.06	12.52	12.42	15.03	14.38	14.24
FeO _t	1.37	1.48	1.28	2.17	1.32	2.12	2.27	0.48	0.70	4.46
MnO	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.07	0.07	0.11	0.07
MgO	0.15	0.16	0.12	0.31	0.14	0.22	0.27	0.07	0.05	0.98
CaO	0.74	0.63	0.54	0.89	0.81	0.86	1.17	0.40	0.61	1.51
Na ₂ O	3.50	3.54	3.42	3.82	3.51	3.42	2.80	5.27	3.65	3.10
K ₂ O	4.78	4.69	4.75	4.54	4.57	4.99	4.48	4.78	5.29	4.26
P ₂ O ₅	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.06	0.02	0.04	0.13	0.28	0.02	0.18
LOI	0.60	0.77	0.33	1.05	0.81	1.20	0.53	0.33	0.54	1.99
Total	100.5	100.5	100.0	100.6	100.1	100.4	100.2	100.3	100.4	100.0
Li	5.07	6.53	14.6	13.5	10.4	7.13	26.8	na	na	55.6
Be	4.98	5.23	4.81	3.50	4.20	2.98	5.12	na	na	3.48
Sc	1.88	1.88	1.44	4.33	2.77	2.48	5.74	na	na	11.4
V	3.60	4.19	3.25	9.34	4.55	5.45	8.29	na	na	30.1
Cr	0.64	0.54	0.57	0.94	0.96	1.35	3.26	na	na	16.1
Co	1.17	0.97	0.80	2.00	0.93	1.19	2.01	na	na	5.70
Ni	0.91	0.89	0.91	0.60	0.68	0.72	2.10	na	na	8.36
Cu	2.78	2.48	4.27	1.68	1.67	1.41	5.94	na	na	11.5
Zn	68.0	29.2	28.0	51.8	30.1	74.2	53.6	na	na	88.5
Ga	21.9	22.7	21.9	23.1	22.7	25.8	20.4	na	na	23.1
Rb	270	259	271	174	260	144	170	na	na	104
Sr	29.7	27.2	18.1	62.3	35.4	47.8	97.2	na	na	133
Y	74.9	80.6	73.4	69.4	79.8	85.7	32.6	na	na	49.1
Zr	218	245	188	376	229	458	331	na	na	628
Nb	22.5	23.3	20.9	23.4	23.3	24.1	20.2	na	na	26.8
Cs	2.47	2.79	4.52	1.91	3.24	1.74	16.5	na	na	3.26
Ba	249	164	119	351	144	314	1047	na	na	949
La	60.0	56.1	50.3	63.6	53.1	71.3	90.9	na	na	71.8
Ce	125	117	105	129	111	153	176	na	na	147
Pr	12.8	12.3	11.5	14.5	12.5	17.3	19.8	na	na	16.9
Nd	46.1	42.8	41.9	53.8	45.3	63.9	75.9	na	na	66.0
Sm	10.1	9.57	9.84	10.6	9.30	14.8	12.5	na	na	12.4
Eu	0.30	0.31	0.25	0.79	0.34	0.88	1.63	na	na	1.89
Gd	9.10	9.31	9.24	10.2	9.37	14.2	8.77	na	na	10.1
Tb	1.79	1.77	1.82	1.73	1.72	2.42	1.20	na	na	1.57
Dy	11.1	11.6	11.5	11.3	11.6	15.1	6.42	na	na	9.26
Ho	2.38	2.48	2.44	2.25	2.43	3.04	1.15	na	na	1.78
Er	7.19	7.60	7.35	6.86	7.68	8.74	3.17	na	na	5.06
Tm	1.24	1.30	1.22	1.05	1.21	1.36	0.45	na	na	0.73
Yb	7.72	7.91	7.53	6.85	8.33	8.31	2.94	na	na	4.81
Lu	1.22	1.22	1.16	0.98	1.18	1.19	0.41	na	na	0.69
Hf	7.37	7.98	6.67	10.1	8.23	12.1	8.62	na	na	14.9
Ta	2.08	2.15	2.22	1.70	2.61	1.09	3.95	na	na	1.69
Pb	43.0	22.9	23.6	19.1	24.8	20.5	28.3	na	na	36.8
Th	34.2	36.5	52.9	25.0	46.4	24.7	28.4	na	na	22.6
U	3.25	3.16	6.96	2.06	3.56	2.06	1.98	na	na	3.99
T _{Zr} (°C)	817	831	808	872	823	889	866	na	na	929

Lithology	K-feldspar granite									
Samples Nan	GQ02-01 ^a	GQ02-02 ^a	GQ02-03 ^a	GQ02-04 ^a	GQ02-05 ^a	GQ02-06 ^a	GQ02-07 ^a	GQ02-08 ^a	GQ02-09 ^a	GQ02-10 ^a
Tectonic Unit	Huaniushan unit									
SiO ₂	75.09	75	75.3	74.69	74.3	75.65	74.58	74.62	74.77	75.33
TiO ₂	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.15	0.15	0.14	0.15	0.14	0.12	0.15
Al ₂ O ₃	13.92	14.15	13.89	14.35	14.42	13.8	14.23	13.25	13.43	13.96
FeO _t	0.61	0.70	0.65	0.67	0.92	0.77	0.70	1.00	0.65	0.65
MnO	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01
MgO	0.31	0.28	0.28	0.35	0.36	0.32	0.33	0.27	0.25	0.33
CaO	0.4	0.23	0.22	0.23	0.23	0.22	0.34	1.01	1.03	0.27
Na ₂ O	3.05	3.15	3.09	3.14	3.16	3.28	3.18	3.32	3.3	3.19
K ₂ O	5.13	5.11	5.21	4.83	4.85	4.39	4.84	4.46	4.87	4.55
P ₂ O ₅	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.05
LOI	1.14	1.02	1.03	1.39	1.31	1.21	1.43	1.65	1.4	1.37
Total	na									
Li	na									
Be	na									
Sc	na									
V	na									
Cr	na									
Co	na									
Ni	na									
Cu	na									
Zn	na									
Ga	21.54	22	22.05	22.26	23.86	22.52	22.29	22.01	20.38	22.04
Rb	418	382	423	369	372	377	396	377	357	387
Sr	49.4	50	48.2	69.4	46.9	43.7	55.8	55.1	40.4	53.7
Y	39.66	42.54	36.62	41.51	46.86	44.42	42.79	34.51	28.18	47.96
Zr	93	100	88	106	107	111	105	107	85	110
Nb	13.74	14.74	14.79	15.58	13.99	13.87	14.68	14.32	11.9	15.49
Cs	29.35	28.46	28.58	30.4	31.95	26.94	28.03	30.96	26.3	28.84
Ba	171	205	158	146	156	149	205	168	148	149
La	18.54	19.82	17.45	20.97	20.32	22.34	20.47	24.44	16.5	20.69
Ce	38.35	42.31	35.74	42.71	42.4	49.27	45.03	49.58	33.42	44.97
Pr	5.01	5.47	4.87	5.59	5.43	5.68	5.36	5.79	3.96	5.43
Nd	19.78	21.38	19.11	21.75	21.65	24.27	23.08	24.21	16.6	23.38
Sm	5.49	5.9	5.06	5.8	6.17	6.31	6.12	5.93	4.27	6.27
Eu	0.41	0.43	0.37	0.38	0.47	0.41	0.44	0.42	0.31	0.43
Gd	5.95	6.25	5.33	6.22	6.8	6.43	5.97	5.69	4.12	6.59
Tb	1.1	1.18	1.07	1.15	1.31	1.34	1.16	1.06	0.83	1.37
Dy	7.1	7.58	6.68	7.48	8.36	8.19	7.33	6.57	4.91	8.81
Ho	1.45	1.56	1.39	1.54	1.72	1.64	1.54	1.34	1	1.82
Er	4.03	4.43	3.83	4.36	4.81	4.58	4.21	3.63	2.9	4.91
Tm	0.6	0.68	0.6	0.67	0.72	0.68	0.64	0.56	0.46	0.73
Yb	3.84	4.31	3.92	4.16	4.54	4.47	4.07	3.69	3.14	4.56
Lu	0.58	0.64	0.58	0.63	0.68	0.66	0.61	0.56	0.47	0.68
Hf	3.73	3.95	3.5	4.05	4.42	4.37	4.05	4.18	3.35	4.22
Ta	3.52	3.71	3.12	3.59	4.55	3.59	3.35	3.14	2.59	3.87
Pb	37.01	35.36	34.46	30.75	28.57	29.34	30.38	37.28	33.87	27.36
Th	21.45	22.25	19.54	21.5	21.75	21.67	21.44	22.16	16.88	22.82
U	3.87	4.27	3.83	4.1	5.24	3.92	4.19	4.08	3.79	4.49
T _{Zr} (°C)	762	770	758	778	778	782	775	763	742	781

Lithology	K-feldspar granite	K-feldspar granite	K-feldspar granite	K-feldspar granite	Granite	Granite	Granite	Granite	Granite	Granite	Granite
Samples Nan	GQ02-11 ^a	GQ02-12 ^a	GQ02-13 ^a	GQ02-14 ^a	B70822-8 ^b	B80624-7.1 ^b	B80624-8 ^b	B80624-9.1 ^b	B80624-9.2 ^b	B80624-11.3 ^l	B70823-7 ^c
Tectonic Unit	Huaniushan unit										
SiO ₂	73.93	75.15	74.86	75.36	76.71	75.05	73.33	73.63	74.67	74.23	77.31
TiO ₂	0.15	0.16	0.14	0.14	0.15	0.11	0.3	0.26	0.17	0.24	0.13
Al ₂ O ₃	13.71	14.02	14.16	13.98	11.64	12.45	12.71	12.66	12.51	12.49	12.43
FeO _t	0.71	0.56	0.68	0.68	1.34	1.28	2.46	1.95	1.51	1.88	0.98
MnO	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.00
MgO	0.25	0.3	0.37	0.29	0.14	0.1	0.35	0.33	0.18	0.26	0.19
CaO	1.05	0.28	0.28	0.38	0.59	0.81	0.8	1.06	0.56	1.03	0.3
Na ₂ O	3.47	3.21	2.95	3.28	3.5	4.17	4.14	3.79	3.83	3.46	3.83
K ₂ O	4.63	4.93	4.96	4.54	4.66	4.70	4.32	5.00	4.90	4.64	5.00
P ₂ O ₅	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.09	0.06	0.08	0.04	0.06	0.04
LOI	1.89	1.21	1.37	1.13	0.41	0.84	1.09	0.8	0.71	0.93	0.49
Total	na	na	na	na	99.3	99.7	99.7	99.7	99.2	99.4	100.8
Li	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
Be	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
Sc	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	1.45
V	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	6.92
Cr	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	2.48
Co	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.56
Ni	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	0.04
Cu	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	3.78
Zn	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	40.21
Ga	22.05	21.38	22.83	23.35	na	na	na	na	na	na	22.94
Rb	401	375	426	384	244	301	185	215	258	216	291
Sr	43.6	52.2	54	51.7	26.65	25.63	57.11	81.00	32.23	60.50	38.8
Y	40.3	36.98	45.27	40.16	61.87	66.76	71.73	55.58	64.24	53.12	64.29
Zr	99	108	112	106	267	201	396	304	236	295	205
Nb	15.27	15.99	13.84	13.23	22.56	25.46	26.17	20.55	20.60	19.99	19.86
Cs	27.88	30.15	28.77	27.01	na	na	na	na	na	na	4.13
Ba	155	181	149	141	162	114	360	405	190	319	137
La	23.36	15.98	18.62	20.09	49.81	34.37	65.10	62.94	42.64	45.75	52.2
Ce	46.8	33.6	38.05	42.12	98.00	76.66	137	127	88.97	92.49	108.26
Pr	5.55	4.42	4.63	4.9	11.12	9.05	15.19	13.74	10.11	10.50	12.15
Nd	23.02	17.59	19.87	20.79	39.81	32.78	55.62	48.87	36.50	38.47	44.51
Sm	5.67	4.94	5.4	5.4	8.55	7.54	11.65	9.55	8.02	8.10	10.19
Eu	0.38	0.37	0.39	0.34	0.33	0.30	0.86	0.79	0.46	0.73	0.44
Gd	5.78	5.5	5.94	5.68	8.39	7.86	11.7	9.36	8.45	8.30	10.01
Tb	1.13	1.1	1.22	1.11	1.51	1.45	1.92	1.51	1.45	1.35	1.68
Dy	7.29	6.78	7.77	6.8	9.53	9.91	12.3	9.51	9.89	8.95	11
Ho	1.52	1.41	1.56	1.38	2.09	2.23	2.55	2.00	2.17	1.87	2.32
Er	4.19	3.88	4.41	3.79	6.53	7.21	7.72	6.00	6.91	5.75	6.98
Tm	0.64	0.61	0.65	0.58	1.03	1.19	1.17	0.92	1.08	0.87	1.12
Yb	4.12	3.95	4.04	3.65	6.57	7.99	7.48	5.78	7.09	5.60	6.63
Lu	0.62	0.59	0.6	0.55	0.95	1.24	1.16	0.90	1.09	0.87	0.98
Hf	3.95	4.23	4.18	3.98	6.61	6.95	9.67	7.30	6.61	7.24	7.12
Ta	3	4.07	3.14	3.28	1.65	2.00	2.00	1.68	1.85	1.64	1.6
Pb	33	28.2	26.97	31.02	17.1	27.9	21.8	21.8	28.3	22.8	23.91
Th	22.12	20.87	18.6	19.24	32.01	54.57	36.84	26.08	35.52	31.78	38.11
U	3.83	4.06	3.94	3.83	2.95	3.60	2.56	2.50	6.43	3.03	4.48
T _{Zr} (°C)	755	776	782	775	836	802	870	839	823	844	816

Lithology	Granite	Granite	Granite	Granite	Syenogranite	Syenogranite	Syenogranite	Syenogranite	Syenogranite	Syenogranite
Samples Nan	B70823-8 ^c	B80626-2 ^c	B80626-3 ^c	B80626-5.1 ^c	HTS-1 ^d	HTS-2 ^d	HTS-4 ^d	HTS-5 ^d	HTS-10 ^d	HTS-11 ^d
Tectonic Unit	Huaniushan unit									
SiO ₂	75.41	73.61	74.45	75.61	76.94	77.48	72.34	78.58	74.37	74.62
TiO ₂	0.17	0.25	0.22	0.18	0.07	0.06	0.26	0.07	0.23	0.22
Al ₂ O ₃	12.15	13.84	13.04	12.15	12.28	11.93	13.4	12.22	13.4	13.33
FeO _t	1.26	1.17	1.54	1.09	0.74	0.65	1.46	0.91	1.64	1.56
MnO	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.03
MgO	0.07	0.37	0.08	0.2	0.06	0.06	0.48	0.09	0.65	0.63
CaO	0.78	0.57	0.23	0.84	0.77	0.68	1.81	0.34	0.56	0.64
Na ₂ O	4.34	4.99	4.65	3.66	3.83	3.83	4.68	6.86	4.36	4.61
K ₂ O	3.67	3.44	4.33	4.41	4.54	4.51	3.20	0.16	3.48	3.23
P ₂ O ₅	0.04	0.09	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.09	0.04	0.1	0.08
LOI	0.97	0.81	0.77	0.89	0.55	0.6	2.05	0.5	1.01	0.9
Total	99.0	99.3	99.5	99.2	100.4	100.5	101.9	100.4	100.9	100.8
Li	na	9.27	2.99	2.15	49.72	35.24	21.23	13.1	20.44	15.44
Be	na	6.56	11.36	4.25	na	na	na	na	na	na
Sc	1.8	3.26	2.58	1.97	na	na	na	na	na	na
V	6.46	22.92	11.72	7.27	na	na	na	na	na	na
Cr	3.05	16	3.6	5.13	24.68	27.47	39.94	32.84	43.15	41.53
Co	0.91	2.09	0.96	1.13	1.33	0.94	3.37	1.09	4.15	3.55
Ni	0.29	7.55	1.74	1.89	3.36	2.22	10.61	3.92	12.08	10.49
Cu	6.33	13.31	7.57	2.78	na	na	na	na	na	na
Zn	42.39	61.36	71.64	86.25	44.59	30.16	99.07	68.19	53.72	64.06
Ga	19.51	25.34	24.82	23.4	33.15	32.19	24.25	32.39	25.82	25.17
Rb	205	292	242	240	628.2	589.6	263.2	15.97	272.4	243.5
Sr	41.2	85.9	61.3	69.8	14.8	18	88.8	20.3	81.6	94.2
Y	62.15	48.78	65.17	64.36	117.7	122.3	61.5	95.7	51.65	55.66
Zr	196	182	226	208	151.8	160.1	182.2	168	162.2	164.5
Nb	22.73	24.42	22.05	20.48	67.23	56.09	25.11	60.91	25.97	23.42
Cs	3.97	8.04	3.3	2.37	na	na	na	na	na	na
Ba	168	93.1	148	146	42.4	41.6	163.7	16.2	164.8	136.6
La	38.08	28.12	53.1	46.27	41.8	37.89	31.8	39.06	32.1	28.3
Ce	80.6	59.13	107.49	95.04	89.93	82.4	69.46	81.57	68.07	62.83
Pr	9.23	6.92	12.25	10.91	9.96	9.13	7.8	9.31	7.74	7.32
Nd	34.2	25.59	44.7	39.98	33.56	30.69	28.64	31.5	27.56	27.21
Sm	8.35	6.47	10.15	9.15	9.03	8.32	6.99	8.3	6.8	6.91
Eu	0.42	0.42	0.44	0.43	0.08	0.07	0.46	0.1	0.45	0.44
Gd	8.81	6.74	10.53	9.54	9.78	8.9	7.07	8.65	6.64	6.92
Tb	1.56	1.2	1.69	1.61	2.15	1.99	1.36	1.96	1.24	1.45
Dy	10.41	8.11	11.19	10.75	15.65	14.58	9.24	14.01	8.03	9.68
Ho	2.22	1.7	2.34	2.26	3.52	3.28	2.01	3.05	1.69	1.97
Er	6.53	5.17	6.98	6.73	11.18	10.85	6.26	9.76	5.16	5.71
Tm	1.1	0.78	1.04	1	2.24	2.31	1.19	2	1	1.07
Yb	6.5	5.09	6.67	6.24	15.35	16.69	7.8	13.71	6.63	6.89
Lu	0.96	0.76	0.98	0.91	2.23	2.45	1.11	1.99	0.99	0.98
Hf	6.85	6.33	6.86	6.57	5.06	5.34	6.07	5.6	5.41	5.48
Ta	2.5	2.2	2	1.7	8.06	6.63	2.75	6.95	2.85	2.65
Pb	24.41	16.82	35.76	25.66	57.76	69.95	150.1	28.4	37.6	34.57
Th	41.08	33.66	47.11	36.99	64	63.2	32.77	47.25	33.42	32.71
U	5.48	4.24	4.15	3.31	32.3	60.8	16.55	4.28	6.26	8.28
T _{Zr} (°C)	805	805	822	812	785	789	789	799	801	800

Lithology	Syenogranite	Syenogranite	Syenogranite	Syenogranite	Syenogranite	Monzogranite	Monzogranite	Monzogranite	Biotite monzogranite	Biotite monzogranite	
Samples	Nan	HTS-12 ^d	HTS-13 ^d	HTS-YT-3 ^d	HTS-YT-4 ^d	HTS-YT-6 ^d	SJP-2γ ^d	SJP-2γ-3 ^d	SJP-2γ-4 ^d	SJP-3γ-1 ^d	SJP-3γ-2 ^d
Tectonic Unit	Huaniushan unit										
SiO ₂	73.69	74.04	73.95	74	74.84	68.8	69.47	69.81	71.97	71.76	
TiO ₂	0.24	0.24	0.23	0.24	0.23	0.43	0.44	0.48	0.3	0.3	
Al ₂ O ₃	13.48	13.42	13.45	13.47	13.16	14.72	14.19	13.96	13.41	13.58	
FeO _t	1.82	1.60	1.38	1.50	1.35	2.73	2.80	3.03	2.68	2.63	
MnO	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.05	0.05	
MgO	0.74	0.65	0.48	0.55	0.49	0.69	0.7	0.76	0.32	0.31	
CaO	0.67	0.77	0.6	0.76	0.74	2.04	1.97	2.06	1.31	1.32	
Na ₂ O	4.43	4.39	4.96	4.64	4.55	3.56	3.27	3.67	3.11	3.13	
K ₂ O	3.59	3.53	3.75	3.53	3.51	5.02	5.19	3.78	5.62	5.7	
P ₂ O ₅	0.09	0.09	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.05	0.05	
LOI	1.06	1.09	0.93	1.05	0.87	1.54	1.51	1.99	0.9	0.89	
Total	100.9	101.0	100.8	100.9	100.7	101.4	101.3	101.8	100.7	100.7	
Li	17.84	12.54	10.46	11.64	10.88	14.73	14.67	26.34	31.82	26.48	
Be	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	
Sc	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	
V	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	
Cr	41.87	40.74	na	na	na	8.45	10.23	10.59	11.34	9.13	
Co	4.44	3.65	2.68	2.54	2.61	4.71	5.02	5.29	3.01	2.71	
Ni	11.93	10.84	8.95	9.32	8.84	3.57	3.96	4.18	3.1	2.18	
Cu	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	
Zn	160.7	103.1	68.49	78.08	64.78	47.01	46.18	52.76	41.87	41.42	
Ga	26.66	24.68	na	na	na	22.2	21.35	22.68	22.71	20.63	
Rb	279.8	270.7	248.7	247.2	246	196.3	200.5	173.4	212.9	215.2	
Sr	102.3	93.5	82.3	84.4	84.4	183.37	177.32	184.58	120.01	119.9	
Y	42.57	42.61	39.53	39.12	36.53	38.83	40.05	46.4	47.44	46.09	
Zr	173.1	168.1	164	171.6	159.1	196.1	204.6	220.3	262.2	269.2	
Nb	27.29	24.91	31.3	31.48	31.96	14.39	14.15	16.33	16.5	16.55	
Cs	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	
Ba	126.9	111.6	165.2	148.9	179.9	592.13	593.45	376.97	605.88	608.08	
La	26.29	30.18	25.49	26.52	25.23	48.79	48.77	57.32	83.51	83.18	
Ce	57.86	65.12	55.58	55.67	52.88	99.05	101	115.8	178	167.7	
Pr	6.74	7.44	6.76	6.71	6.34	11.54	11.76	13.69	19.52	19.1	
Nd	24.67	27.01	24.66	24.15	23	41.01	42.06	48.76	68.83	67.12	
Sm	6.06	6.47	6.09	5.74	5.74	7.89	8.35	9.65	12.63	12.54	
Eu	0.4	0.43	0.43	0.42	0.42	1.34	1.3	1.2	1.15	1.11	
Gd	5.87	6.25	5.95	5.76	5.69	6.88	7.14	8.65	10.1	10.31	
Tb	1.16	1.26	1.09	1.04	1.05	1.17	1.17	1.47	1.62	1.64	
Dy	7.14	7.29	6.76	6.43	6.21	6.62	6.98	8.36	8.84	8.81	
Ho	1.43	1.41	1.25	1.22	1.14	1.29	1.31	1.61	1.58	1.62	
Er	4.05	4.06	3.91	3.72	3.49	3.94	4.08	4.81	4.96	4.96	
Tm	0.74	0.72	0.66	0.64	0.59	0.62	0.63	0.75	0.81	0.78	
Yb	4.78	4.82	4.4	4.37	4.01	3.9	3.98	4.66	5.51	5.28	
Lu	0.71	0.7	0.65	0.64	0.6	0.56	0.55	0.65	0.79	0.77	
Hf	5.77	5.6	3.9	4.5	3.9	5	5.1	5.5	6.9	6.1	
Ta	2.92	2.75	2.65	2.51	1.72	1.63	1.57	1.87	1.95	2.06	
Pb	67.75	43.53	32.9	58.8	33.8	23.1	29.3	21.8	29.8	31.3	
Th	33.86	36.92	32.99	27.69	30.77	27.15	28.24	34.45	48.26	45.02	
U	10.71	10.46	6.91	5.49	13.5	4.47	4.82	6.47	4.02	3.87	
T _{Zr} (°C)	803	800	791	799	793	796	800	811	828	831	

Lithology	Biotite monzogranit e	Biotite monzogranit e	Biotite monzogranit e	Biotite monzogranit e	Biotite monzogranit e
Samples Nam	SJP-3γ-3 ^d	SJP-3γ ^d	D004 ^e	D005 ^e	D006 ^e
Tectonic Units	Huaniushan unit		Hongliuhe suture		
SiO ₂	72.53	71.37	73.27	72.78	68.86
TiO ₂	0.27	0.33	0.3	0.29	0.58
Al ₂ O ₃	13.4	13.7	13.75	13.8	14.1
FeO _t	2.24	2.42	1.94	2.16	4.16
MnO	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.07
MgO	0.28	0.38	0.48	0.39	0.81
CaO	1.23	1.36	1.71	1.32	2.3
Na ₂ O	3.07	3.14	3.71	3.38	3.29
K ₂ O	5.96	6.03	3.32	4.6	3.82
P ₂ O ₅	0.04	0.05	0.05	0,05	0.14
LOI	0.69	0.92	1.12	0.78	1.48
Total	100.5	100.7	100.6	100.4	101.0
Li	28.14	22.01	10.6	8.02	14.1
Be	na	na	1.5	1.46	2.4
Sc	na	na	6.43	6.59	9.52
V	na	na	na	na	na
Cr	8.79	5.31	na	na	na
Co	2.21	2.57	2.66	2.28	6.08
Ni	1.97	1.33	na	na	na
Cu	na	na	na	na	na
Zn	40.12	40.39	na	na	na
Ga	20.96	22.59	38	47.4	39.1
Rb	204	219.4	74.6	122	111
Sr	113.19	121.88	135	102	165
Y	33.24	40.06	20.9	25.8	41.5
Zr	231.3	273.9	264	255	301
Nb	13.93	17.13	7.7	7.51	12.4
Cs	na	na	2.01	1.4	2.67
Ba	613.69	680.68	1290	1780	1180
La	73.16	86.66	49.6	46	50.4
Ce	157.3	175.9	119	122	116
Pr	17.28	19.96	11	10.9	12.2
Nd	59.96	69.92	40.2	40.6	47.3
Sm	10.64	12.49	6.64	7.32	9.13
Eu	1.18	1.23	1.16	1.21	1.57
Gd	7.99	9.62	5.81	6.4	8.34
Tb	1.25	1.52	0.83	0.97	1.37
Dy	6.35	7.86	4.8	5.7	8.5
Ho	1.15	1.41	0.92	1.12	1.72
Er	3.41	4.08	2.5	3.02	4.82
Tm	0.5	0.58	0.38	0.46	0.74
Yb	3.24	3.62	2.55	3.04	5.03
Lu	0.47	0.52	0.35	0.42	0.66
Hf	6.2	7	7.5	7.32	8.32
Ta	1.1	1.39	0.5	0.58	1
Pb	29.9	32.6	na	na	na
Th	44.15	49.25	9.23	9.62	12.3
U	3.59	4.09	1.13	1.08	1.6
T _{Zr} (°C)	816	829	840	835	841

Note: The samples 16BS118 and 16BS119 obtained no trace element compositions as they suffered from heavy alteration. na means no data is available.

^aDing, J., Han, C., Xiao, W., Wang, Z., Yang, X., 2015. Geochemistry and U-Pb geochronology of tungsten deposit of Huaniushan island arc in the Beishan Orogenic Belt, and its geodynamic background. *Acta Petrologica Sinica* 31, 594-616 (in Chinese with English abstract).

^bLi, S., Wang, T., Tong, Y., Hong, D., Ouyang, Z., 2009. Identification of the Early Devonian Shuangfengshan A-type granites in Liuyuan area of Beishan and its implications to tectonic evolution. *Acta Petrologica et Mineralogica* 28, 407-422 (in Chinese with English abstract).

^cLi, S., Wang, T., Tong, Y., Wang, Y.B., Hong, D.W., Ouyang, Z.X., 2011. Zircon U-Pb age, origin and its tectonic significances of Huitongshan Devonian K-feldspar granites from Beishan orogen, NW China. *Acta Petrologica Sinica* 27, 3055-3070 (in Chinese with English abstract).

^eWang, H., Ren, W., Zhao, Q., Liu, Z., Wang, T., Zhao, H., 2016. Geochemical characteristics and Tectonic Significance of A-type Granite in the South Margin of Zhaobishan, Beishan Area. *Northwestern Geology* 49, 39-48 (in Chinese with English abstract).

^dZhu, J., Lv, X., Peng, S., 2016. U-Pb zircon geochronology, geochemistry and tectonic implications of the early Devonian granitoids in the Liuyuan area, Beishan, NW China. *Geosciences Journal* 20, 609-625.